

Interaction Studies in Binary Liquid Mixtures using different Theories of Viscous Flow

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An attempt has been made to compare the relative merits of Hind *et al.*, Frenkel and Naidu relations for theoretical evaluation of viscosity in binary liquid mixtures of 1,1,2-tetrachlorethane with benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, cyclohexane and acetone at 303.15 K. The study has been extended to investigate the intermolecular interaction between unlike molecules in terms of excess free energy of mixing.

Interaction studies in binary liquid mixtures have been made by several workers^{1,2}. But very few attempts have been made^{3,4} to study the interaction from viscosity data. Recently, Nath and Dubey⁵ and Nath and Tripathi⁶ have analysed their viscosity data in the light of Bloomfeld and Dewan theory⁷. Very recently Pandey *et al.*⁸ have applied the different theories of viscous flow to multicomponent liquid mixtures. The purpose of the present paper is two fold: firstly, to study the relative merits of viscosity relations of Hind *et al.*⁹, Frenkel¹⁰ and Naidu², and secondly to study the intermolecular interactions operating between different components of liquid mixtures of TCE+benzene, TCE+toluene, TCE+*p*-xylene, TCE+cyclohexane and TCE+acetone with the viscosity data of Nath⁵ and Tripathi⁶.

A number of empirical equations have been proposed to correlate the viscosities of liquid mixtures in terms of pure component data by many investigators¹¹⁻¹³. These equations have been critically analysed and reviewed by Irving¹¹ and by Reid *et al.*¹². Irving in a thorough and critical analysis on the effectiveness of the several equations, found that Grunberg Nissan¹⁴ equation is the best descriptive equation to correlate the viscosities of binary liquid mixtures. The work of Katti and Chaudhuri³ based on theoretical work of Eyring¹⁵, is very useful to calculate excess molar Gibb's energy of activation of flow, which depends upon size, shape and chemical nature of component molecule in the liquid mixture. Bloomfeld and Dewan⁷ in their viscosity relation have combined the absolute reaction rate theory¹⁵ and the free volume theory¹⁶. The absolute reaction rate theory relates the viscosity to the free energy required by a molecule to overcome attractive force field of its neighbour so that it can jump to a new equilibrium position, hence the deviation of experimental value from simple logarithmic additive value of viscosity is related to free energy of mixing or excess free energy of mixing ($\epsilon \Delta F_m$). Nath and Tripathi⁶ have not evaluated

this excess free energy of mixing from their viscosity data for the above binary mixtures. Further, Bloomfeld and Dewan have used Flory's statistical theory¹⁷ to evaluate the entropic and free volume contribution to the mixture viscosity. But Flory's theory is most suitable for spherical molecules. Hence in the present communication the viscosity relations of Hind *et al.*⁹, Frenkel¹⁰ and Naidu² have been used to understand the non-ideality behaviours. These relations correlate the viscosities of liquid mixtures simply in terms of pure component data and no extra parameters are needed.

Theoretical: Using the concept of fluidity of mixtures as given by Glasstone *et al.*¹⁸, the excess free energy of mixing is represented by the relation,

$$\epsilon \Delta F_m = -RT \{ \ln \eta_{m(s)} - \ln \eta_{m(i)} \} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is a constant independent of temperature and composition and may have value ranging from 0.4082 to 1 and $\eta_{m(s)}$ and $\eta_{m(i)}$ are the viscosity of the mixture and that of ideal mixture respectively. Hind *et al.*⁹ made use of the following expression for the viscosity of a binary mixture,

$$\eta_{mix} = x_1^2 \eta_1 + 2x_1x_2 \eta_{12} + x_2^2 \eta_2 \quad (2)$$

Taking into consideration the interaction between the molecules, Frenkel¹⁰ and Naidu² developed the following logarithmic relations for non-ideal binary liquid mixtures,

$$\ln \eta = x_1^2 \ln \eta_1 + x_2^2 \ln \eta_2 + 2x_1x_2 \ln \eta_{12} \quad (3)$$

$$\log \eta_{mix} = x_1 \log \eta_1 + x_2 \log \eta_2 + 2x_1x_2 \log \eta_{12} \quad (4)$$

where, η_{12} is the viscosity at equimolar concentration and which is obtained by the relation,

$$\eta_{12} = 0.5\eta_1 + 0.5\eta_2 \quad (5)$$

Results and Discussion

The experimental values and theoretically computed values of viscosity of TCE with benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, acetone and cyclohexane at 303.15 K are given in Table 1. The excess free energy of

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL AND THEORETICALLY COMPUTED VALUES OF VISCOSITY AND EXCESS FREE ENERGY OF MIXING ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) OF BINARY MIXTURES OF 1,1,2,2-TETRACHLOROETHANE AT 303.15 K

x_2	$\eta \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				$\alpha\Delta F_m$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	Exptl.	Eqn. (2)	Eqn. (3)	Eqn. (4)	
CHCl₃CHCl₂+Benzene					
0.086 8	0.611	0.640	0.621	0.612	-0.154
0.114 1	0.628	0.664	0.641	0.628	-0.492
0.400 9	0.835	0.929	0.869	0.829	-3.187
0.452 8	0.885	0.970	0.915	0.872	-5.338
0.552 3	0.984	1.053	1.006	0.959	-8.088
0.586 4	1.019	1.090	1.039	0.990	-8.631
0.603 1	1.035	1.105	1.055	1.006	-8.583
0.714 7	1.155	1.207	1.164	1.118	-9.340
0.761 1	1.205	1.247	1.211	1.169	-8.840
0.878 6	1.335	1.353	1.333	1.304	-6.349
CHCl₃CHCl₂+Toluene					
0.104 8	0.581	0.619	0.594	0.579	-0.652
0.230 8	0.667	0.737	0.691	0.658	-2.615
0.304 2	0.725	0.807	0.752	0.709	-4.507
0.357 5	0.771	0.857	0.798	0.749	-6.125
0.431 4	0.836	0.926	0.865	0.809	-7.271
0.520 3	0.919	1.010	0.949	0.886	-7.966
0.691 2	1.111	1.171	1.122	1.058	-11.258
0.769 7	1.198	1.245	1.206	1.149	-9.808
0.802 2	1.239	1.276	1.241	1.188	-9.822
0.908 8	1.365	1.376	1.366	1.328	-6.458
CHCl₃CHCl₂+<i>p</i>-Xylene					
0.116 5	0.633	0.670	0.645	0.633	-0.727
0.144 5	0.653	0.695	0.666	0.650	-1.858
0.234 3	0.714	0.775	0.734	0.709	-2.848
0.300 6	0.769	0.835	0.787	0.756	-5.664
0.329 9	0.788	0.861	0.811	0.778	-4.795
0.402 1	0.851	0.926	0.873	0.833	-6.879
0.451 8	0.897	0.970	0.916	0.874	-8.238
0.483 9	0.927	0.999	0.945	0.901	-8.838
0.552 3	0.993	1.060	1.008	0.962	-9.728
0.621 0	1.064	1.122	1.073	1.026	-10.726
0.701 9	1.145	1.195	1.153	1.107	-9.832
0.751 2	1.200	1.239	1.202	1.160	-9.844
CHCl₃CHCl₂+Cyclohexane					
0.153 8	0.867	0.919	0.906	0.928	8.368
0.174 3	0.871	0.932	0.918	0.942	10.195
0.402 6	0.969	1.078	1.056	1.103	17.115
0.502 5	1.027	1.143	1.119	1.171	16.503
0.607 6	1.097	1.210	1.188	1.241	15.202
0.659 3	1.145	1.243	1.223	1.274	11.943
0.743 5	1.213	1.297	1.280	1.326	9.674
CHCl₃CHCl₂+Acetone					
0.019 5	0.312	0.318	0.321	0.303	-6.254
0.119 6	0.408	0.435	0.390	0.348	-33.485
0.154 0	0.444	0.475	0.407	0.365	-40.919
0.104 6	0.477	0.510	0.433	0.331	-46.614
0.222 4	0.518	0.555	0.466	0.403	-52.177
0.304 6	0.621	0.650	0.543	0.455	-61.925
0.325 4	0.648	0.675	0.561	0.469	-67.061
0.354 0	0.684	0.708	0.594	0.480	-69.150
0.447 5	0.839	0.817	0.697	0.566	-82.910
0.557 2	0.990	0.946	0.831	0.676	-80.165
0.583 6	1.021	0.996	0.865	0.705	-77.489
0.606 1	1.051	1.002	0.894	0.732	-75.711
0.760 0	1.234	1.182	1.107	0.950	-54.084
0.821 1	1.296	1.253	1.196	1.057	-41.791
0.995 1	1.411	1.366	1.365	1.297	-17.256

x_1 represents the mole fraction of the first component.

mixing ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) have also been recorded. A perusal of Table 1 indicates that Frenkel and Naidu relations give very satisfactory results which are very

close to the experimental values of viscosity. The excellent results of these relations are due to the fact that they incorporate all possible major interactions. Hind's relation, though considers the possible interactions, gives comparatively larger deviations. This discrepancy is due to the fact that this relation takes into account the simple additivity of viscosities of the components whereas the viscosities of the mixtures follow the rule of logarithmic additivity and hence it results in higher values of viscosity.

It is interesting to note that for the systems TCE+aromatic hydrocarbons and with cyclohexane, Naidu's relation gives better results at lower mole fraction of TCE whereas Frenkel's relation gives better results at higher mole fraction of TCE. The values of excess free energy of mixing ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) is negative for the systems TCE+benzene, TCE+toluene, TCE+*p*-xylene and TCE+acetone and positive for TCE+cyclohexane system. The greater negative values of ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) for the system TCE+acetone show that TCE forms strong molecular complexes with acetone in the liquid state. The positive values of excess free energy of mixing for the system TCE+cyclohexane indicate weak interaction and the values of ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) for the systems TCE with aromatic hydrocarbons suggest that TCE forms weak complex with these hydrocarbons because the π -electron clouds, above and below the ring, certainly inhibit the interaction between the components to some extent and result in virtually ideal behaviour of the mixture.

The various types of interactions that are operating between molecules of different systems are dispersion forces, charge transfer, hydrogen bonding, dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole interactions. The negative values of ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) for TCE+benzene, TCE+toluene and TCE+*p*-xylene can be attributed to the predominance of contributions of dispersion, dipolar and induced forces over the specific interaction between the components. The positive values of ($\alpha\Delta F_m$) for TCE+cyclohexane indicate the presence of dispersion forces and its greater negative values for TCE+acetone suggest that acetone forms strong molecular complexes with TCE.

It is quite certain that spectroscopic methods are widely used in modern studies to understand about molecular interactions. Early studies in this field were done by Hildebrand and Glascock¹⁸ who found that the extent of interaction between iodine and aromatics is increased with the introduction of more and more electron-donating groups on the aromatic ring. The most notable work in this field are due to Mulliken and his collaborators¹⁹. Nath and Dubey⁶, and Nath and Tripathi⁶ have studied the interactions trichloroethylene with aromatics and tetrachloroethane with aromatics respectively from viscosity measurements and from the thermodynamic data derived from sound velocity. They reached to the conclusion that the strength of interaction is increased with the introduc-

tion of CH₃ group to the aromatic ring. These results are in agreement with the results of modern technique of spectroscopic methods.

References

1. J. H. HILDEBRAND and R. L. SCOTT, "Solubility of Non-electrolytes", Reinhold, New York, 1950; E. A. GUGGENHEIM, "Mixtures", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1952; I. PRIGOGINE "Molecular Theory of Solutions", North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1959; K. C. REDD, S. V. SUBRAHMANYAM and J. BHIMSENACHAR, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 1964, **19**, 559; R. P. RASTOGI, J. NATH and J. MISHRA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 1277; R. P. RASTOGI, J. NATH and J. MISHRA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 2524.
2. P. R. NAIDU and V. R. KRISHNA, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 1965, **20**, 1954.
3. P. K. KATTI and M. M. CHAUDHARY, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1964, **9**, 1442.
4. P. K. KATTI, M. M. CHAUDHARY and O. PRAKASH, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1966, **11**, 593; R. K. NIGAM and B. S. MAHAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **9**, 1225; R. K. NIGAM and M. S. DEILLON, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, **8**, 1260.
5. J. NATH and S. N. DUBBY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1980, **84**, 2166.
6. J. NATH and A. D. TRIPATHI, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1986, **24**, 541.
7. V. A. BLOOMFIELD and R. K. DEWAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 3113.
8. J. D. PANDHY, N. AGRAWAL, SHIKHA and K. MISHRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, **29**, 113.
9. P. R. HIND, E. MCLAUGHLIM and A. R. UBBELHODE, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 328.
10. J. FRENKEL, "Kinetic Theory of Liquids", Oxford University Press, London, 1946.
11. J. B. IRVING, "Viscosity of Liquid Mixtures", NEL Reports 630 and 631, 1977.
12. T. M. REID, J. M. PRAUSNITZ and B. E. POLING, "The Properties of Gases and Liquids", 4th. ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1987.
13. J. R. PARTINGTON, "An Advanced Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1954.
14. L. GRUNBERG and A. H. NISSAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1949, **45**, 125.
15. S. GLASSTONE, K. J. LAIDER and H. EYRING, "The Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1941, Chap. 9.
16. A. K. DOOLITTLE, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1952, **22**, 1471; **23**, 236; M. L. WILLIAMS, R. F. LANDEL and J. D. FERRY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 3701; M. M. COHEN and D. TUMBULL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **31**, 1164.
17. P. J. FLORY *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1833; A. ABÉ and P. J. FLORY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1838.
18. J. H. HILDEBRAND and B. L. GLASCOCK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 26
19. R. S. MULLIKEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 600; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 801; R. S. MULLIKEN and W. B. PERSON, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **13**, 107; R. S. MULLIKEN and W. B. PERSON, "Molecular Complexes", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1969.